

**International Peer Review
Journal**

p-ISSN 1817-5562
e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)
CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Volume 4 Number1 April 2008

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer-review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor : Salih M Al Hasnawi
Minister of Health

Founding Editor : Aamir Jalal Al Mosawi
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www.newiraqijm.4f.com

Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus
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Extensively drug – resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB) in Kashmir, India

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Extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis (XDR-TB), a recently recognized entity, defined as resistance to at least rifampicin and isoniazid in addition to any fluoroquinolone, and at least one of the injectable drugs (capreomycin, kanamycin and amikacin) has emerged worldwide as threat to public health and tuberculosis control raising concerns of a future epidemic of virtually untreatable TB [1-6].

Gandhi and Co-workers [4].reported the experience with XDR-TB in Kwa Zulu Natal, South Africa and found it to the magnitude of 10% among MDR cases. During 2000-2004, the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)

and the WHO surveyed 17,690 TB isolates among which 20% were MDR and 2% were XDR. Similarly, population based data on drug susceptibility of TB isolates obtained from the United States (for 1993-2004), Latvia (for 2000-2002) and South Korea (for 2004), revealed that 4%, 19% and 15% of MDR-TB cases, respectively, were XDR-TB [1].

As per the current reports from India, prevalence of multi-drug resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) ranges from around 3% in new cases to 12% in treated patient. However, there are no published reports of XDR-TB from this country so far.

From March 2003 to February 2007, we studied 910 cases of pulmonary tuberculosis at the Government Chest Disease Hospital – a tertiary care respiratory centre associated with the Government Medical College Srinagar, Kashmir, India. Among these 386 (42.4%) cases were smear positive. Sputum culture and drug susceptibility testing was performed in suspected cases of MDR-TB. Overall 52 (5.74%) patients were found to have MDR-TB, out of which 8 (15.3%) cases had XDR-TB according to the prescribed definition (Table 1).

All the 8 patients had been previously treated for tuberculosis. One patient (number 44) was found to have associated HIV and one patient (number 16) was resistant to all the second line drugs, classified as XDR-M [1]. 7 of these patients died during the course of hospital stay and one (number 20) although classified as XDR-TB, continues to have favorable response to other drugs as per the sensitivity, who got converted to smear negative by sixth month of treatment and is under regular follow up. Pneumothorax was the associated illness in half of the cases. To our knowledge, the present study represents the first report from India.

To conclude, XDR-TB is a serious and emerging public threat globally, especially amongst the population with increased prevalence of HIV infection. Activities for more effective and rapid diagnosis, and new treatment regimens, are needed in near future to counteract this disaster. In addition, more and more population-based studies are needed to describe the magnitude and future course of this virtually untreatable form of tuberculosis.

References

1. Centers of Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Emergence of *mycobacterium tuberculosis* with extensive resistance to second-line drugs – worldwide, 2000-2004. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2006 Mar 24; 55(11): 301-5.
2. Wise J. Southern Africa is moving swiftly to combat XDR-TB. *Bull World Health Organ* 2006 Dec; 84(12): 924-5.
3. Raviglione MC, Smith MI. XDR-tuberculosis – implications for global public health. *N Engl J Med* 2007; 356: 656-58.
4. Gandhi NR, Moll A, Sturm AW et al. Extensively drug-resistant tuberculosis as a cause of death in patients co-infected with tuberculosis and HIV in a rural area of South Africa. *Lancet* 2006; 368: 1575-80.
5. Arora VK, Sarin R, Singla R et al. DOTS – plus for patients with multidrug resistant tuberculosis in India: early results after three years. *Indian J Chest Dis Allied Sci* 2007; 49: 75-79.
6. Masjedi MR, Farnia P, Sorooch S et al. Extensively drug – resistant tuberculosis : 2 years of surveillance in Iran. *Clin Infect Dis* 2007; 44: 888-9.

Table – 1
Profile of Patients with XDR-TB (n=8)

No	Age	Sex	Sensitivity Panel											Associated Illness	Outcome	
			H	R	Z	E	S	Ofx	Cs	Eto	Cfz	Am	Km			
4	42	M	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	-	Hypothyroidism	Died (septicemia)	
8	60	M	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	S	S	-	R	Pneumothorax	Died (massive hemoptysis, respiratory failure)	
16	48	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	Pneumothorax	Died (Pulmonary thromboembolism)	
19	50	M	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	-	Diabetes mellitus Pneumothorax	Died (septicemia)	
20	24	F	R	R	S	S	R	R	S	S	S	R	R	-	-	Still alive, smear negative
24	20	F	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	-	R	Ethionamide induced hypothyroidism Pneumothorax	Died (Myxedema coma, cardio-pulmonary arrest)	
31	29	F	R	R	R	S	S	R	-	S	R	R	R	Pneumothorax	Died (respiratory failure)	
44	42	F	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	S	-	R	-	HIV	Died (at home)	

H, isoniazid; R, rifampicin; Z, pyrazinamide; E, ethambutol; S, streptomycin; Ofx, ofloxacin; Cs, cycloserine; Eto, ethionamide; Cfz, clofazimine; Am, amikacin; Km, kanamycin; S, sensitive; R, resistant